

Gamma is Unavoidable: Correcting the Display of Microscopy Images

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Adjusting brightness&contrast of microscopy images is considered standard practice, but what about the other important adjustment knob: gamma? Because display screens expect gamma-corrected images, failing to adjust gamma of a scientific image distorts the brightness of the displayed data. We argue that, far from dubious image manipulation, gamma correction helps ensure proper reproduction and visualization of images.

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Introduction

There is an information-transmission problem in all digital imaging. Natural scenes (and microscopes) produce analog light signals and scientific cameras digitize that signal with very high precision, but displaying the data requires sending it through a low-bandwidth bottleneck: the 8-bit display pipeline that includes file formats, computer monitors, and printers. This process necessarily loses some information, and our challenge as image analysts is to allocate those 256 gray levels of the computer monitor in a manner that best conveys the scene to the ultimate viewer. There are two primary image controls that help us achieve this: one is adjusting brightness&contrast; the other is gamma.

What is brightness&contrast?

The first challenge is to select the range of pixel intensity values to display in your digital image, which is accomplished by adjusting brightness&contrast. High-precision scientific cameras include enough available intensity levels (e.g. 65,536 for 16-bit) to approximate the analog luminance range of the microscope, but computer monitors can only display 256 different intensity levels. So the high-precision intensity data must be downsampled in a way that computer monitors can display and the human eye can perceive, but preserves the scientifically important information. Because microscopy images are often dim, simply mapping the entire 65,536-value range evenly into 256 bins results in most of the information collapsing into the first few gray values, producing an image that appears completely black. This is precisely what happens when you open a 16-bit microscopy image in Photoshop, Illustrator, or PowerPoint, which blindly convert the entire 16-bit range to 8-bit.

Instead, to effectively view the subset of gray values that actually matter (i.e. not the noise and none of the levels higher than the brightest pixel in your image), brightness&contrast windowing is essential for microscopy images. Image analysis programs like ImageJ/Fiji and napari natively display 16-bit images by adjusting the brightness&contrast without modifying the actual pixel values.^a *Brightness* sets the center of the window of values to be rebinned, while adjusting *contrast* changes the window's width. Equivalently, you can adjust the minimum and maximum of the range, the lower gray value that will be set to black (0) and the upper brightness level that will be assigned to white (255).

What is gamma?

While brightness&contrast adjustment evenly redistributes pixel values across the 256 levels, *gamma* is a nonlinear remapping: each pixel's numeric value is raised to the gamma power ($I_{\text{out}} = I_{\text{in}}^\gamma$, where I_{out} is the pixel intensity in the output image, I_{in} is the normalized raw pixel value, and γ is gamma). When gamma < 1, dim portions of the image become more visible; for gamma > 1, dim parts are suppressed (including background and noise, but also possibly dim but real structures) and the contrast between bright portions is enhanced (Figure 1).

While everyone concedes that (reasonably) adjusting brightness&contrast is necessary and appropriate, many researchers and journals strongly discourage adjusting gamma on the grounds that it is a nonlinear adjustment. However, this position stems from an incomplete picture of how scientific cameras, raw image formats, colorspace intensity encoding, and computer monitors interact. Counterintuitively, *not* adjusting gamma on a scientific image actually results in a nonlinear rendering of your data.

^a Converting to 8-bit (by selecting Image→Type→8-bit or clicking the "Apply" button in the brightness&contrast window in Fiji) irreversibly rebins the actual intensity numbers. So while converting to 8-bit may be necessary to display properly when making figures for a paper, it is essential to do any quantitative image analysis on the raw image file before converting to 8-bit.

Why adjust gamma?

You may have noticed that what you see by eye through the oculars often looks better than how the images appear on the screen. This occurs for multiple reasons, including limited field of view, camera pixelation, grayscale display, and the fact that the human eye is a very sensitive detector with locally adaptive dynamic range. But another important contributor is the lack of *gamma correction* in scientific imaging.

As described above, the (nearly) continuous luminance information from the microscope and high-bit-depth camera must be quantized to 8-bits for the computer monitor, a downsampling that necessarily results in some loss of information. The straightforward approach of creating 256 equal bins is inefficient, because human vision is nonlinear: we perceive *changes relative to the baseline* rather than absolute differences, meaning that small changes are more detectable in dim regions than in bright ones.^b As a result, when you convert a 16-bit image or an infinite-bit analog signal to only 8 bits, the steps at the low end of the range appear too coarse to the human eye (Poynton, 1996).

The solution is to reallocate gray levels from the highlights and toward the shadows, resulting in narrower binning at lower levels where the tonal precision is needed, and wider bins at the bright end of the scale where larger jumps are needed before they are perceptible. Visual perception follows a power law, with an exponent of 0.3–0.5 (Stevens, 1957). Therefore, a so-called “gamma correction” of 0.45 during 8-bit conversion results in more uniform proportional changes between gray levels across all 256 levels instead of equal absolute steps, quantizing information so that the loss is concentrated in regions where the eye is least sensitive (Poynton, 1996). In other words, gamma correction allocates 8-bit’s limited bandwidth to better match human vision.

To ultimately display the gamma-corrected data in a manner that accurately reflects the original scene’s linear luminance, the display system must perform a subsequent gamma decoding of $1/0.45 = 2.2$.^c Coincidentally, cathode-ray tubes have just such a nonlinear response to electron-beam intensity, so physics automatically relinearizes the gamma-encoded image (Poynton, 1996; Rasnik et al., 2013). Modern LCD and OLED monitors perform this reverse gamma step by default using color management to emulate the sRGB transfer function (which can be roughly approximated by a gamma of 2.2, <https://www.w3.org/Graphics/Color/sRGB>).

^b Specifically, Weber’s Law states that a just-noticeable difference in gray levels is a constant fraction of approximately 1% across a range of brightnesses. So with only 256 equal bins, one step at level 20 is a whopping 5%, while one step at level 250 is only 0.4%, well below the just-noticeable difference threshold. Because of this, shadows will show visible banding or contour lines and highlights waste tones on indistinguishably small steps.

^c While this round-trip gamma correction/decoding may seem to get us right back to where we started, it does so in a way that minimizes information loss at the 8-bit quantization step by taking into account the sensitivity of the receiver, the human visual system. Gamma correction is fundamentally about how to transmit continuous data through a limited number of levels.

Figure 1. Gamma correction better matches the nonlinear sensitivity of human vision and compensates for the computer monitor’s inherent gamma, but is not universally necessary. Left is gamma = 1, and right is after gamma correction of gamma = 0.45. **(A)** For samples with both bright and dim objects, gamma correction of 0.45 results in dim objects no longer getting lost in the background, and bright objects are not as saturated. **(B)** When the primary objects are all bright, applying a gamma correction may be unhelpful. In this case, the computer monitor’s inherent gamma of 2.2 actually helps suppress background noise and enhances the contrast between differently bright regions. (WARNING: An image with gamma applied by changing pixel values is no longer appropriate for quantitative analysis; perform all analysis on raw image files.)

Consumer cameras for photography perform sRGB gamma correction when they save a JPEG file, precompensating for the subsequent gamma of computer monitors (Figure 2A). Conversely, microscope detectors (scientific CCDs, sCMOS, PMTs, APD, SPADs, etc.) are designed and calibrated to have a linear output range (Rasnik et al., 2013) and are typically saved in TIFF format^d with a gamma of 1. This ensures that intensity differences in the image can be correctly quantified: an object that is twice as bright as another in the microscope will be recorded as pixels with twice the value in the TIFF file. However, when a TIFF from a scientific camera is displayed on a computer monitor, the net effect is an image with a gamma of approximately 2.2—or that of the computer monitor itself—because the camera does not correct for the monitor’s inherent gamma (Figure 2B). So when we create images directly from microscopes, we must manually adjust gamma if we want the resulting display to be linear on a computer monitor (Poynton, 1996).^e

^d The TIFF format can also store gamma encoding and color profiles, so it is more complicated than TIFF=linear. But most scientific cameras and image processing software output TIFFs with linear gamma.

^e Color-managed applications, like Photoshop, can assign a linear color profile to an image, and the operating system’s color management system

Figure 2. Computer monitors have a gamma of approximately 2.2. **(A)** Consumer cameras save their images as JPEGs with a built-in gamma of roughly 0.45 (or $1/2.2$) to precompensate for the computer monitor's gamma. The net effect is that the monitor's pixel brightness corresponds approximately linearly to the original scene's luminance. **(B)** Scientific cameras have a linear output. Therefore, when a TIFF from a scientific camera is displayed on a computer monitor, the net effect is an image with a final gamma of approximately 2.2, or that of the computer monitor itself. (Adapted from <https://www.cambridgeincolour.com/tutorials/gamma-correction.htm> and Poynton (1996).)

When you actually apply a gamma of 0.45 to a microscopy image, you will notice that both dim and bright portions of the image are more discernible (Figure 1A). This is because the computer monitor buries the dimmer objects into the background or saturates the bright areas; a gamma-corrected image not only shows a closer representation of the microscope's luminance output but also makes the data easier to parse by eye. For these reasons, gamma correction not only benefits the viewer, *it is actually a more accurate display of scientific data.*

But gamma correction is not strictly required. If the scientifically important regions of your sample are all sufficiently and similarly bright, adjusting gamma may not be beneficial. In fact, the higher gamma of computer monitors can enhance the perceived contrast of brighter regions (Poynton, 1996), so images with a diffuse but elevated background might look better without gamma correction (Figure 1B). Just be careful not to artificially bury real but dim structures into the background by failing to consider gamma.

will adjust the monitor gamma appropriately. In Photoshop, for example, one can go to Edit→Assign Profile and select a linear RGB profile, or create one via Edit→Color Settings→Working Spaces→RGB→Custom RGB with gamma set to 1.0. The downstream display pipeline will then adjust to display linearly. Most scientific imaging software, however, does not participate in color management and simply passes pixel values directly to the display pipeline, which assumes they are sRGB-encoded and renders them with an effective gamma of ~ 2.2 .

How to adjust gamma

The standard, but non-ideal, way to adjust gamma in ImageJ/Fiji is to go to Process→Math→Gamma and set the value to 0.45. **WARNING:** This approach is destructive, as it changes the actual pixel intensities, so you should perform all intensity comparisons or quantitative analysis on the raw image files before modifying the gamma.

Instead of modifying the actual pixel values, a better approach is to apply a gamma correction by remapping the lookup table (LUT) to have a nonlinear range of gray colors (e.g., https://github.com/ndefrancesco/macro-frenzy/blob/master/color/gammify_LUT.ijm). To make this method even easier, we made the Gamma LUT Toggle tool for ImageJ/Fiji (https://sites.imagej.net/Gamma_LUT_Toggle/) (Figure 3). In napari, the gamma slider in the main GUI window also changes the LUT without modifying the underlying pixel data. Some napari and Python commands are available in the supporting information.

Figure 3. The *Gamma_LUT_Toggle* tool in Fiji nondestructively toggles between a LUT with gamma of 0.45 and 1. To install it in Fiji, go to Help→Update... and select "Manage Update Sites", then check the box next to "Gamma_LUT_Toggle" and restart Fiji. The function will appear under the red >> symbol on the Fiji toolbar and will add a button with a small gamma (γ) symbol. When you click the button, it will apply a nondestructive gamma of 0.45 by remapping the LUT while maintaining the underlying pixel values. Clicking the button a second time will toggle the image back to the original linear LUT. It works with grayscale as well as single-color LUTs.

In general, here is a workflow for adjusting image levels:

1. Open a raw TIFF or other raw file format in an appropriate image analysis software
2. Adjust brightness&contrast
3. Do all quantification now (before any conversion)
4. Apply gamma 0.45 for display
5. Convert to 8-bit
6. Export for figures (do not overwrite original raw data files)
7. The display pipeline will automatically perform the gamma 2.2 relinearization for you via color management (or physics, if you're still using a CRT)

For multi-channel pseudocolored images, be sure to apply the same gamma for each color channel. For multi-panel figures where it is important to compare object brightness between images, apply the same brightness&contrast range and gamma to each panel.

How to report gamma adjustments

Despite the case for gamma correction, it is still necessary to report any gamma adjustment or nonlinear LUT in the image caption or methods section. This will allow future researchers to better replicate your results. Transparent reporting also helps spread the idea of using gamma correctly.

While most journals require gamma adjustments to be disclosed in the figure caption or methods (Cromey, 2010; Rossner and Yamada, 2004), the Microscopy Society of America considers gamma correction a non-reportable image manipulation, akin to brightness&contrast adjustment (<https://microscopy.org/Scientific-Data/Standards>). A reasonable compromise is to report a standard gamma correction once in the methods, not in every image caption. For example, your methods section could include the following statement: “Images were adjusted for optimal brightness&contrast, and gamma was set to 0.45 to compensate for the nonlinear gamma of computer monitors. All intensity measurements were performed on raw image files before gamma correction or conversion to 8-bit. Raw 16-bit TIFFs are provided with the supporting information.”

However, if you decide to adjust gamma to a value other than 0.45, it is best to include such nonstandard adjustments directly in the figure captions for those images. Note also that multicolor LUTs (e.g., “fire”) are often nonlinear in an inconsistent manner: not only can the shading of each color be nonlinear, but the human eye is more sensitive to some colors than others, doubly confounding the linearity of the displayed image. Nonstandard gamma changes or unpredictably nonlinear LUTs need to be documented clearly in the caption or methods, and grayscale versions should be provided in the supporting information.

Conclusion

You cannot avoid gamma. Publishing images without any gamma correction simply accepts the nonlinear rendering imposed by the computer monitor. Correcting linear scientific images with a gamma of 0.45 precompensates for the built-in gamma of the display pipeline, using the limited 8-bit budget to faithfully reproduce both bright and dim features as the viewer would perceive them at the microscope with their own eyes. Alongside brightness&contrast, gamma should be employed to improve the faithful reproduction and visualization of data.

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Supporting Information

The code for the ImageJ/Fiji Gamma Toggle Tool can be found at Github (https://github.com/samjlord/Gamma_LUT_Toggle) and a static version is here:

```
var gammaApplied = false;
var origReds, origGreens, origBlues;
macro "Gamma LUT Toggle Action Tool - C000T4b12y" {

    if (nImages == 0) {
        showMessage("Error", "No image open.");
        exit();
    }

    // Check if image is RGB
    if (bitDepth() == 24) {
        showMessage("Error", "This tool does not work with RGB images.\nPlease convert to grayscale first
        (Image > Type > 8-bit).");
        exit();
    }

    if (!gammaApplied) {
        // Store original LUT
        getLut(origReds, origGreens, origBlues);

        // Apply gamma = 0.45
        getLut(reds, greens, blues);
        gamma = 0.45;

        for (i = 0; i < 256; i++) {
            reds[i] = round(255 * pow(reds[i]/255.0, gamma));
            greens[i] = round(255 * pow(greens[i]/255.0, gamma));
            blues[i] = round(255 * pow(blues[i]/255.0, gamma));
        }

        setLut(reds, greens, blues);
        gammaApplied = true;
        showStatus("Gamma 0.45 ON");

    } else {
        // Restore original LUT
        setLut(origReds, origGreens, origBlues);
        gammaApplied = false;
        showStatus("Gamma 1.0 (original)");
    }
}
```

Here are some napari commands to create an 8-bit gamma-corrected image for display purposes:

```
# Run in a Python session while napari is open (napari-env active):
import napari
from skimage import io, exposure
import numpy as np

viewer = napari.current_viewer()
layer = viewer.layers[0] # or: viewer.layers['your_layer_name']

# Apply standard gamma correction
gamma_corrected = exposure.adjust_gamma(layer.data, gamma=0.45)

# Convert to 8-bit
data_8bit = ((gamma_corrected - gamma_corrected.min()) /
             (gamma_corrected.max() - gamma_corrected.min()) * 255).astype(np.uint8)

# Preview in napari before saving
viewer.add_image(data_8bit, name='8-bit with gamma 0.45')

# Save when satisfied
io.imsave('figure_gamma8bit.tif', data_8bit)
```

Or, for multi-channel images:

```

# For multi-channel images, apply the same gamma to all channels:
for i, layer in enumerate(viewer.layers):
    gamma_corrected = exposure.adjust_gamma(layer.data, gamma=0.45)
    data_8bit = ((gamma_corrected - gamma_corrected.min()) /
                 (gamma_corrected.max() - gamma_corrected.min()) * 255).astype(np.uint8)
    io.imsave(f'channel_{i}_gamma_corrected.tif', data_8bit)

```

This is also easy to do directly in Python:

```

from skimage import io, exposure
import numpy as np

# Load the image from disk
image = io.imread('your_input.tif')

# Apply standard gamma correction (cast to float to preserve precision)
gamma_corrected = exposure.adjust_gamma(image.astype(np.float32), gamma=0.45)

# Convert to 8-bit
data_8bit = ((gamma_corrected - gamma_corrected.min()) /
             (gamma_corrected.max() - gamma_corrected.min()) * 255).astype(np.uint8)

# Save
io.imsave('figure_gamma8bit.tif', data_8bit)

```

For multi-channel images (if your stack is (Y, X, C) instead, swap stack[i] for stack[..., i]):

```

from skimage import io, exposure
import numpy as np

stack = io.imread('multichannel.tif') # assume shape (C, Y, X)

for i in range(stack.shape[0]):
    channel = stack[i]

    gamma_corrected = exposure.adjust_gamma(channel.astype(np.float32), gamma=0.45)

    data_8bit = ((gamma_corrected - gamma_corrected.min()) /
                 (gamma_corrected.max() - gamma_corrected.min()) * 255).astype(np.uint8)

    io.imsave(f'channel_{i}_gamma_corrected.tif', data_8bit)

```